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Regulatory Issues with AI-enabled medical devices

Issue/Problem

Innovative AI-enabled medical devices have presented a regulatory challenge to the FDA, as the agency's current approval and regulation process is not equipped to manage devices equipped with adaptive AI and machine learning capabilities.

Description of the Problem

The FDA's goal is to balance the need to ensure that such devices remain safe and effective for patients, without requiring burdensome new regulatory submissions for approval with each change.

Results

On December 4th, the FDA issued its final [Marketing Submission Recommendations for a Predetermined Change Control Plan for Artificial Intelligence-Enabled Device Software Functions](#), completing a drafting process that began in April 2019. The FDA's guidance outlines a process through which manufacturers submit predetermined change control plans (PCCPs) with their marketing applications. PCCPs provide descriptions of planned changes to AI-enabled devices and how those changes are assessed, streamlining the regulatory approval process and fostering the innovation of new treatments.

Lessons Learned

The guidelines are recommendations, not legally enforceable, for manufacturers. The regulatory scheme governing the development of AI-integrated medical treatments and devices must remain flexible to adapt to future developments, as the ability of these devices to adapt to patient circumstances in real time represents an opportunity to improve patient outcomes but requires sufficient regulatory oversight to ensure that any problems with nascent technologies are pre-emptively addressed.